

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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This article is focused on the application of artificial intelligence in an educational environment. It looks at the latest technology, which is already playing a huge role for both teachers and students. Also, the topic of the future of artificial intelligence in education is touched upon.

Keywords: *information technology; artificial intelligence; education.*

There are now many Artificial Intelligence (AI) programmes to help with education, with which students, pupils and teachers benefit enormously. A great advantage is that the educational platform is adapted to meet the needs of the students. The AI software development system helps academics to work on their weaknesses. In the process, the software detects where the student is having difficulties and sends the necessary materials to improve skills. Adaptive learning uses a basic AI algorithm. It is also a great advantage for the learner to be able to learn at any time of the day. There are now well-known AI- based programmes. Let us consider them.

Automatic grading. A specialised computer programme based on artificial intelligence that simulates the behaviour of a teacher grading essays written in an educational environment. It can assess students' knowledge, analyse their answers, give feedback and draw up individual learning plans.

Intermediate learning interval. This programme reassesses knowledge that you may have forgotten. Its essence is that the AI keeps track of what you have learned and when. It is therefore able to find out information that you may have forgotten and recommends that you repeat it.

Feedback for teachers. For many years, teachers have been evaluating each other, but this is no longer done by means of paper documents, but increasingly by the use of chatbots with AI. They are able to collect opinions through an interactive interface like a real interviewer. It is also able to explain the reasons for opinions.

Virtual assistants. Virtual assistants for teachers already exist, capable of responding accurately and quickly to students' queries thanks to built-in AI-computers.

Campus Chat. This project can help students who have just arrived on campus to get settled in. Campus Chat is always happy to explain how to get to the right office, how and where to give the right documents.

Personalised learning. Personalised learning refers to a variety of educational programmes in which the pace and approach to learning are optimised for the needs of each student. The experience takes into account the learning preferences and specific interests of different learners. Artificial Intelligence has no problem matching the pace to the learner's needs so that he or she can better absorb the programme.

Adaptive learning. It assumes that the AI is able to track each student's progress and either adjust the course or inform the teacher of material that is difficult for the individual student to understand.

Proctoring. Distance learning usually involves distance learning examinations. However, it is necessary to ensure that the student writes the exam given to them independently. For this purpose, AI-based protection systems come to the rescue. Proctoring or Proctored Test is a mechanism that ensures the authenticity of the test taker and prevents him/her from cheating through the proctor who is present during the test.

Data accumulation and personalisation. Already now, AI is capable of suggesting the nearest cafés of interest based on the geolocation of the individual. The same technology can be applied when we are learning, based on examples only from the area we are interested in.

Progress in AI and machine learning is impressive, but it is far from the limit of what is possible. There are plenty of good ideas that AI can bring to fruition. Overall, AI can greatly improve education systems through its ability to optimise many parts of a teacher's work and automate others, ultimately giving them more and more time to spend with their students.

Reference list

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